

THE APPLICATION OF PROJECT BASED LEARNING IN CLASSROOM.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139075>

In recent years institutions of higher education have been trying to provide students with both hard skills, namely cognitive knowledge and professional skills, and soft skills, such as problem-solving and teamwork. However, these skill related goals are not easy to be achieved as traditional learning has been playing a prevailing role where teachers are “the transmitter of the knowledge” while students act as “the receptor of the information. As a result, it is difficult for students to fully engage in educational practices, which may lead to a superficial understanding of disciplinary knowledge.

Besides, universities, and research universities, in particular, are more focused on the cultivation of students’ research skills rather than professional skills or transferable skills. Thus, this might cause a gap between what students learn at the university and what they need in the workplace. In order to change this situation, it is suggested that students are provided with the opportunity to participate in real problem-solving and knowledge construction in authentic professional contexts. One attractive way to achieve this goal is through project-based learning (PjBL).

“Education thus becomes an act of depositing, in which the students are the depositories and the teacher is the depositor. Instead of communicating, the teacher issues communiques and makes deposits which the students patiently receive, memorize, and repeat. This is the ‘banking’ concept of education, in which the scope of action allowed to the students extends only so far as receiving, filing, and storing the deposits. They do, it is true, have the opportunity to become collectors or cataloguers of the things they store. But in the last analysis, it is the people themselves who are filed away through the lack of creativity, transformation, and knowledge in this (at best) misguided system. For apart from inquiry, apart from the praxis, individuals cannot be truly human. Knowledge emerges only through invention and re-invention, through the restless, impatient, continuing, hopeful inquiry human beings pursue in the world, with the world, and with each other.”

Rather than viewing students as empty vessels in need of academic ‘deposits’ that are gatekept by teachers following a ‘sage on the stage’ approach, PBL seeks to disrupt traditional, lecture-driven methods by situating students at the center of a relevant problem or issue, and granting them more agency in developing, testing, and revising solutions.

PBL is consistently proving to be effective in classrooms of all ages. U.S. News recently shared an article mentioning studies that have yielded positive outcomes at the college/university, high school, and elementary school levels — specifically, students in classes taught with a PBL approach are out-performing their peers on standardized tests. These gains have been consistent across racial and socioeconomic groups.

PBL can be implemented with in-person, hybrid, and remote learning; at any grade level; and, within any content area. We realize that many teachers are curious about PBL, but unsure of where to start. With that in mind, we've curated our most popular articles on project-based learning for teachers at all levels of experience and implementation. From teachers who are brand new to PBL, to those who are looking to amplify the outcomes of existing units, as well as successful exemplars from classrooms around the country, we hope that you are able to find at least several resources to help you better engage your students and improve your teaching by centering project-based learning at the core of your curriculum. "From a teacher's perspective, Project-Based Learning is a method of structuring curriculum around projects to promote learning of prioritized academic content. These projects highlight the process of learning itself by offering authentic, inquiry-based activities for learners to access content, share ideas, and revisit their own thinking."

Types of projects. There are various ways PBL can be characterized and sorted out. It depends on many factors including the age of students, their level and interest, the constraints of time and space or the level and the extent of teacher's experience with PBL. William Kilpatrick, the founder of the project method, distinguished only four types of project work, in consideration of the aims. First, there were problem-based projects, where intellectual problems were solved, then construction-based and evaluation-based projects and finally drill-based ones, which were aiming at gaining a certain skill. The thing is that the best starting point for any project is generally considered the so called spontaneous projects which are the projects that are proposed by students themselves. These projects have very strong motivation potency, students elaborate on problems that relates to real students' interests and it ensures their maximum involvement, at least at the beginning of project work. However, it seems that there are not so many opportunities for the origins of such kind of projects in the classrooms. For another thing, there is also an opinion that despite the fact that contemporary students face several problems in their personal lives they are used to seeking the answers to them elsewhere but in the school lessons.

Then, even though spontaneous project are actually the only right projects to carry out, considering the core the PBL definition, in the educational practice teachers operate mainly with two different initial procedures. Firstly, they come up with the topic, elaborate it in advance, prepare all the materials and then present it to students as project work. Or, in the second place, teachers come up with the topic or a problem, students accept it and elaborate it themselves with the help of teachers. Kratochvílová strictly distinguishes these two approaches and the former one considers as a principle of TT whereas the latter still fulfils the basic of PBL idea and its goals. It is this stage where the teachers decide whether project is their or students 'enterprise; unquestionably PBL and TT start differing here also in the aims, output, motivation of students, roles of teachers and demands on students as well as methods of assessment.

Organizing PBL in English Classes. It emerges that although PBL offers students great space for autonomy, it must not be considered as unprepared improvisation which is orientated solely on student's interest. Quite on the contrary, PBL is necessary to plan for one thing from the viewpoint of time and position of the project within the curriculum, for another planning should cover the knowledge of the educational goals that should be met and level of their difficulties. Preparation is the key to making project work a success and Hutchinson argues that the understanding of project work and the ability to deal with it lies in learner-centered characteristic of PBL which dwells not in the question What?, but rather in the question Who? Who makes the decisions? It has been mentioned above that spontaneous projects are rare, so it is usually the teacher who provides the basic topic, nevertheless the content and the product are determined principally by the learners who on the one hand are given the space for creative work and independent decisions, yet, on the other hand, all that happens in a carefully prepared teacher's plan. The planning itself represents very demanding activity for teachers, yet in comparison with TT, teachers do not plan in advance students' activities as such but merely the essential outline for the whole project work, the main stages, their interconnections plus all the documentation that is important to fill in and store. The first thing to consider when introducing PBL into the lessons Svobodová et al. claim that is indispensable to get ready in three areas. The first thing to ponder is whether students are ready for this kind of method. It is not correct to present PBL method to them without any preliminary practice. The second point is that teachers who have never implemented any project work are not likely to lead students towards a successful realization of PBL and therefore must

familiarize with the issue of it and correspondingly gather information from more experienced teachers or their work. And the third point is that teachers should plan very carefully their first project work, so called “pilot project”, which sounds as a matter of course, however, according to the authors, there are still many cases in which project work was realized with little or no preparation.

In conclusion, PBL helps students to increase their knowledge potential and to form independent thinking skills, so its application in the field of education helps to increase the teaching potential of the teacher.

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